

**AYURVEDIC MANAGEMENT OF AMAVATA WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO
RHEUMATOID ARTHRITIS - A CASE STUDY****Dr. Mahesh Ashokrao Patil*, Dr. Arati Datye**

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ABSTRACT

Aamvat is an Ama pradoshaja vikara, caused by Agnimandya, which leads to accumulation of Ama in Shleshmasthan and Prakopa of Vata dosha, resulting in pain, stiffness and swelling of joints, which closely resembles the chronic inflammatory autoimmune disorder called Rheumatoid arthritis. Prevalence of rheumatoid arthritis is approximately 0.8% worldwide and 0.5-0.75% in India. Amavata is result of Agnidushti, Amotpatti & Sandhivikruti, since of those treatment which normalize Agni, metabolize Ama & controls Vata & keep up sound Sandhi & Sandhista Shleshma will be best for this disorder. Rheumatoid arthritis (RA) is a symmetric polyarthritis that. In various studies, the treatment helps to relieve the symptoms, but the underlined pathology remains untreated because the treatment is ineffective and also causes many side effects & toxic symptoms. Amavata management concept has Dravya, Katu-Rasa, Dipan Pachana with Langhana, Swedana and Tikta as Shaman Chikitsa, laghuvirechan, anuloman helps to relieve symptoms of aamvat. In this article, case series represent two cases aamvata which get significant result by mahavatvidhans ras and shunthi churn given as anuloman Dravya. There was no side effect observed during and after the treatment. Therapy gives significant relief in symptoms of Aamavata.

KEYWORDS: Amavata, Ama, Rheumatoid arthritis, Anuloman.**INTRODUCTION**

In the present time due to modern life style, unhealthy eating habits, hectic schedule and stress, incidence of Ama related diseases are increasing. One of the most common disease is Amavata. In Ayurveda, Madhavkar first mentioned Amavata as a separate disease. The word Amavata has two components i.e., Ama and Vata. These two components contribute to the morbidity and disease process in Amavata. The main causative factor Ama is formed due to malfunctioning of the digestive and metabolic mechanisms. Ama with Vata gets localized in the body. The prevalence of the disease is approximately 0.8% of the total population worldwide (range 0.3% to 2.1%) with male and female ratio of 1:3. The onset is most frequent during the fourth and fifth decades of life, with 80% of patients developing the disease between age group of 35 and 50. Ayurveda provide long lasting effect in aamvat and better result with shaman and anuloman chikitsa.

MATERIALS AND METHODS**Case 1**

A 38 yr female patient housewife by occupation visited the OPD of Kayachikitsa dept of M.A.P.H Hospital with presenting sign and symptoms as follows -multiple joint pain, stiffness and swelling over bilateral lower limbs, bilateral interphalangeal joint pain and swelling over the joint.

H/o present illness - patient was having above complaints since 6-7 years which patient gradually increased in 6 months. She had H/O allopathic medicine taken for rheumatoid arthritis Patient took treatment in under rheumatologist, but did not get significant relief so for proper treatment and for panchkarma patient came to podar hospital.

Patient had no any significant comorbidities.

S/H/O- Appendectomy 16-17 yrs back

H/O- Addiction to masher 2-3 times/ day since 20 yrs.

N/H/O - PR bleeding / Piles/Fissure/Fistula

GENERAL EXAMINATION

GC – Moderate	Pallor - +3
BP – 110/80 mmhg	Icterus - absent
P -78 /min	Clubbing – absent
T-97.3 F	Cyanosis - absent

P/A - Non tender, mild gaseous distension

Rs - AEBE Clear

CNS -S1,S2 N

ASHTAVIDHA PARIKSHA

Nadi – 78/min	Shabda - Spashta
Mal – Samyak	Sparsh – Khar, Ruksha, Ushna
Mutra – Samyak	Druk – Prakrut
Jivha - niram	Akruti – Madhyam

Investigation report

Hb-11.5mg/dl, HCT -38 %, MCV -83.7 fl, MCHC - 31.1g/dl, PLT - 398

Samprapti

Criteria of Assesment

Sr no	Gradation 3	Gradation 2	Gradation 1	Gradation 0
Pain (multiple joint pain)	Severe pain	Moderate pain	Mild pain	Painless (bearable)
Swelling (swelling over the joints)	Severe swelling	Moderate swelling	Mild swelling	No swelling
Temperature	Severe temp	Moderate temp	Mild temp	No temp
Tenderness	Severe	Moderate	Mild	No tender
Stiffness (morning)	For 6-7 hr	For 4-3 hr	For 2-3 hr	For 1-2 hr

Treatment

1. Shaman aushdi -

Sihanad gugul 2-0-2

Rasnasaptak kwath 20 ml BD

2. Anuloman - Mahavatvidhwans ras 3 tab + 1/4 spoon shunti churn with koshana jala given as anuloman Dravya.

Maahvaatvidhwans rasa contains parad, gandhak, naag, vanga, loha, Tamra bhasma, abharak bhasma, pimpali, tankan, sunti, mire, jaypal, vatsnabh etc and bhavna dravya triktu, triphala, chitrak, bhrungraj, limbu nirugundi.

Mahavatvidhwansan rasa acts on vatvahini Nadya and reduce kshobha of vatvahini Nadya and also acts on shoth and ruja. Mahavatvidhwansan ras acts as sookmasrtogami, pramathi, strong aampachak, ras -rakta dhatwagnideepan and shothahar (due to vatahar properties).

Shunti which is deepan, amapachan and enters the minute strotas (channel) it breaks the vibandh of vata and kaph.

By giving combination of maahvatvidhwans ras and shunthi churn for anuloman it acts on Sam kaph (thus reducing pain and shotha).

RA-positive, lipid profile, liver function test, kidney function test -WNL

Hetu of Aamvata

1. Viruddha ahara, viruddha vihara.

Snigdha aahar sevan after heavy exercise (High protein, fats intake and excises, gym)

- leads to vatvruddhi.

2. Diwaswapa after having meals

- leads to kaphpittaprakop

3. Jatharagnimandya

Heavy diet [sweet, heavy milkshake]

(Kheer, icecream, sweets,)

Leads to kaphaprakop

4. (heavy exercise, weight lifting, heavy physical work)

- Kaphasnachiti, vatvruddhi.

Mode of action of sinhanad guggulu

Majority drugs of sinhnad gugul have deepan (enzyme activating), amapachan (biotoxin reducing), shooghna (analgesics), jwarghana (antipyretic), balya (energy enhancing) and aamvat har properties. It enhances the Agni bala (digestive and metabolic capacity and alleviates the ama (biotoxins) and prevents the further ama (formation in body). This reduces the clinical manifestations of amvata (rheumatoid arthritis) and helps in breaking samprapti (pathogenesis) of amavata.

Rasnasaptak kwath has amapachan properties which helps in breaking samprapti and relives symptoms of amvata.

Pathya

Aharaj - yava(barley) kulatha (horse gram), raktshali (rice), shigru (drumsticks), punarnava, adarak (ginger) Viharaj - sunlight exposure for atleast 15 minutes in a day, pranayam yoga mediation, Apathya - aharaj - flour of mash (black gram), rajmash (kidney beans), sweets, fast food uncooked food, salty spicy, oily food, fish, curd, jaggery.

Viharaj - daytime sleeping, supression of natural urges, exposure to cold wind.

RESULTS

Sr. No	Before treatment (Anuloman with shaman aushdhi)	After treatment
Pain	Grade 4	Grade 1
Swelling	Grade 3	Grade 1
Temperature	Grade 4	Grade 0
Tenderness	Grade 2	Grade 1
Stiffness	Grade 4	Grade 2

CONCLUSION

Hence the drug choosen by me works on amavata decreasing the sandhishool, sandhishooth, sandhisahithilya within less duration and without causing side effects and also it is one of the best cost effective treatment.

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